

Research Article

EasyConveyor

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Abstract: As the worldwide business grows, many companies invest in innovative technology to enhance the operation. The main process in exporting and importing products is by using the conveyor. Unfortunately, the current conveyor is not as efficient as it could be. Thus, our company invented the “EasyConveyor”, a conveyor that can be broken down into modular sections, allowing easy assembly and disassembly. This feature would be particularly useful in environments where space is constrained or for temporary installations such as pop-up factories or construction sites. The conveyor operates using rechargeable batteries that can eliminate the need for fixed power sources or complex wiring. The system of this conveyor could integrate wireless controls for speed adjustments and other operational parameters. This feature makes it easier to adapt the conveyor to different tasks without physical adjustments. By using “EasyConveyor”, we can minimize cost, save time and use less energy.

Keywords: conveyor; innovative technology; product management

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today’s fast-moving industries, flexibility and efficiency are more important than ever. Whether it’s in manufacturing, warehousing, or logistics, companies need systems that can easily adapt to changes in workflow, product sizes, or operational demands without slowing down or requiring expensive adjustments. Traditional conveyor systems, while useful, can be rigid and complicated to install, making them less suitable for workplaces that are constantly evolving. This is where the Customizable Modular Conveyor System comes in—a smart solution designed to meet the needs of modern businesses. The system is made up of individual conveyor units that can be easily connected to create a conveyor belt of any length or shape. Whether you need a straight line, an incline, or a path with curves, this system can be quickly adjusted to fit your space and process.

Each conveyor unit has wheels, making it easy to move around different areas like factory floors or warehouses. This flexibility is perfect for businesses that need to move materials efficiently or change their workspace layout frequently. The system’s built-in motors and simple controls allow

operators to adjust speed and direction easily, ensuring smooth operation. It's also portable, making it great for temporary setups or places that require frequent reconfiguration. The beauty of the system lies in its adaptability. As businesses grow or processes change, additional units can be added without any hassle. This minimizes downtime and eliminates the need for a permanent setup, which in turn helps boost productivity.

To ensure safety and efficiency, the system includes features like anti-slip wheels and synchronized sensors to prevent accidents and keep everything running smoothly. This means businesses can focus on moving their products more quickly without worrying about delays or mishaps. In short, this customizable conveyor system offers a practical, user-friendly solution for industries looking to improve how they handle materials. It's versatile, portable, and cost-effective, making it the ideal choice for businesses that need to stay flexible and efficient in a competitive environment.

A customizable conveyor system is designed to attach to each other and offers flexibility, scalability, and ease of use for any industries that use conveyors to operate their task. The concept revolves around modular units that can be easily linked together to form a conveyor belt of any desired length or configuration. Each conveyor unit is equipped with wheels or tires that enable the entire assembly to move across factory floors, warehouses, or other locations where material handling is necessary. This system is ideal for businesses looking to streamline their production lines, warehouses, or material handling processes.

Those are the steps on how to use the conveyor, starting by determining the layout that best suits your operational needs. Each module comes with connectors that allow for quick and secure attachment to the next and making it simple to assemble. By simply connecting more units, the conveyors may be expanded or changed, allowing businesses to react quickly to changes in manufacturing procedures, product size, or increasing demand. This adaptability lowers reconfiguration-related downtime and eliminates the requirement for permanently installed conveyor systems. Whether you need a straight path, an incline, or a more complex shape with curves and turns, the conveyor modules can be adjusted to fit the space and process flow. The system also allows for easy disassembly, which makes it highly portable and perfect for changing work environments.

Each conveyor unit has an integrated motor that powers it, enabling it to operate alone or as a component of a larger system. Operators may change the speed, direction, and other important factors as needed thanks to the machines' straightforward, easy-to-use controls. Furthermore, the units' tires enable the conveyor system as a whole to travel effortlessly from one place to another, which makes it perfect for temporary installations or activities requiring mobility.

The conveyor functions similarly to any other belt after it is attached together, but its true benefit is its capacity to change to meet the demands of the company. Additional modules may be added as manufacturing need rises, and the conveyor can be readily modified if space needs to be rearranged. The modules include integrated sensors and motors that work in synchronize to guarantee seamless operation and avoid misalignments or bottlenecks. Efficiency and safety are also prioritized in the design. Because of the anti-slip technology built into the tires, there is no low chances of an accident as the system moves across a variety of surfaces. By cutting down on the amount of time required to move items between various manufacturing stations, the flexibility to adjust the pace and layout increases productivity. This conveyor system is appropriate for a variety of uses, such as manufacturing, storage, and logistics, due to its versatility, portability, and user-friendliness. It may greatly increase operating efficiency and cut expenses by providing on-the-fly modification and cutting down on setup time.

1.1 Problem Statement

A basic tradition conveyor system is an option that is often used in industry to move goods from one place to another. However, the main disadvantage of this type of conveyor is that its position cannot be changed. It means that, when the order of the production process or the layout of the factory changes, the conveyor cannot be easily modified to adapt to the new requirements. This complicates adaptation to operational changes, as well as requiring cost and time for assembly and disassembly if it needs to be moved. On the other hand, flexible conveyor that can be joined and moved according to the user's wishes is more flexible and easy to adapt. It allows the arrangement of the conveyor to be modified as needed, such as increasing the length or changing the direction of the flow of goods. This makes custom conveyors a more efficient and effective option, especially for companies that need flexibility in their daily operations. Overall, flexible conveyors offer greater flexibility and usability than limited basic conveyors.

1.2 Objectives

The traditional conveyors are usually fixed in size and layout, making them difficult to reconfigure for different tasks or adapt to spaces with unique dimensions or a small space. EasyConveyor works to increase productivity by providing a modular conveyor solution that is easy to assemble, disassemble and reconfigure to meet specific operational needs. EasyConveyor also is innovated to increase flexibility and adaptability. It allows a user to customize the conveyor length and configuration with each separate modular section. Thus, it is very practical for temporary setups and various environments like construction sites and pop-up factories.

This product utilizes rechargeable batteries to reduce reliance on electricity, thereby promoting energy efficiency and cost saving. EasyConveyor is definitely a smart choice in saving on energy costs and minimizing infrastructure requirement. Furthermore, it offers a convenient setup and teardown process by helping users save time and reduce labor costs associated with installation and maintenance and automatically reducing setup and maintenance time. Additionally, the main objective of innovating this product is to simplify operational controls. EasyConveyor integrates wireless controls for easy, remote adjustments to conveyor speed and settings that enables quick adaptation to different tasks without the need for physical modifications. Therefore, EasyConveyor is a better version compared to the old ones that will not only reduce the energy cost but also save time for installation and maintenance cost.

2. NOVELTY

For the flexible conveyor system, rubber and lithium iron phosphate (LiFePO₄) are ideal materials to use as each has their benefits that will improve the conveyor's strength and capability. Due to the high durability and flexibility the rubber conveyor belt is best utilized with heavy or abrasive material handling. The natural grip of the component keeps small items from slipping while in transit, thus keeping items in position as they slide along the conveyor. Also, as rubber the material allows such benefits as free flexibility for the conveyor layout including curves, as well as absorbing shock within both the conveyor and the items being conveyed. The use of rubber is also desirable across a range of temperatures and can also be resistant to many chemical and oil operations which are typical in many operations. PVC is relatively lighter and cheaper than rubber, but not as tough, best suited for applications which do not involve intense pressure, on the other hand PU is tough, food grade, but lacks temperature bearing capability of rubber and its grip.

As a source of power for the conveyor, LiFePO₄ battery is favorable since its long lasting life span ranges from 2000- 4000 cycles while standard lithium ion batteries can only provide 300-500 cycles. This durability makes the LiFePO₄ batteries economical for applications that often involve charging such as conveyors. They are also relatively stable, and possess less likelihood of exploding than a traditional lithium ion battery, though of course this comes with the downside of a lower energy density. LiFePO₄ batteries deliver a relatively constant power during the range of the discharge cycle, thereby maintaining the conveyor speed. Environmentally, LiFePO₄ batteries are advantageous since toxic elements are in lesser quantities and the batteries are simpler to recycle compared to other lithium based batteries. Lithium-ion batteries are less massive but shorter-lived, and relatively more hazardous than LiFePO₄ in terms of thermal runaway issues, on the other hand are affordable than LiFePO₄ but heavyweight, shorter lived and less efficient. Rubber belts combined with LiFePO₄ batteries provide a low-maintenance, safe, reliable technology that is ideal for high usage and modular conveyors.

3. COMMERCIALIZATION POTENTIAL

Traditional conveyor systems frequently face challenges in dynamic work environments because of their inflexibility, complicated installation procedures, and restricted scalability, which complicate adjustments for varying product sizes and workflows. The significant upfront costs and high expenses associated with modifications can discourage businesses that require adaptability. Besides that, maintenance issues and a lack of compatibility with modern technologies further limit their efficiency. Therefore, these factors result in a lack of flexibility, rendering traditional systems less appropriate for fast-paced operations that demand efficient material handling and rapid adjustments. To prevent these problems and protect sensitive goods, it is essential to use EasyConveyor as it offers several key advantages that enhance its utility across various industries.

Those are the reasons why we developed EasyConveyor. This innovative solution has significant commercial potential. Firstly, its detachable nature provides increased flexibility, allowing for easy reconfiguration, expansion, or reduction based on the specific needs of the work site, making it suitable for logistics, construction, and manufacturing. Secondly, the battery-powered design enhances mobility, enabling use in remote locations without readily available power and facilitating easy relocation within a facility. Thirdly, the conveyor reduces downtime, as operations can continue during power outages without the need for a constant power supply, and rechargeable batteries can be swapped to ensure continuous operation.

Additionally, it boasts space efficiency, as it can be disassembled and stored compactly when not in use, making it ideal for operations with limited storage or those requiring temporary setups. Lastly, the ability to charge the battery using renewable energy sources supports sustainability goals and helps reduce the carbon footprint of operations. In industries where temporary setups, mobility, and flexibility are essential, this type of conveyor has the potential to revolutionize the deployment and management of material handling systems.

4. BENEFITS TO COMMUNITY

“EasyConveyer” offers several features and benefits to the community. Firstly, it has a modular design for flexibility that can be easily combined or separated as needed. It is particularly useful for companies that operate in areas with limited space or are constantly changing. For example, a company that operates in pop-up factories or construction areas, can quickly set up the conveyor and evacuate it when it is no longer needed to suit different layouts or production needs. This modularity helps

companies that must quickly adapt to changing requirements or site conditions, thus enhancing productivity and quick responses to market demand. Other than that, “EasyConveyor” utilizes rechargeable batteries that can eliminate the need for constant power sources or common wire layouts. This is specifically beneficial when common power supplies are unavailable or unstable such as in distant locations or emergency responses sites. The absence of complex wiring can reduce deployment, decreased set up time and safety risks. Furthermore, the ability to recharge the batteries allows activities to continue continuously without being limited to a specific place. This feature enhances mobility and accessibility for a business to work in a diverse environment more effectively in places that lack infrastructure. The “EasyConveyors” overall design emphasizes accessibility, sustainability and adaptability making it a valuable tool for a variety of communities and industries.

5. FEEDBACK FROM COMMUNITY

Based on the survey results, a significant majority of 25 out of 30 respondents choose “No” and emphasized that they never heard of mobile and detachable conveyor systems like EasyConveyor before this.

Figure 1. Results of questionnaire distributed among UiTM students

Additionally, an overwhelming majority of 28 out of 30 respondents agreed that they would consider using a battery-powered conveyor system for their worksite or factory. This underscores that the use of battery-powered conveyor is a practical benefit for a company.

Figure 2. Results of questionnaire distributed among UiTM students

Moreover, 17 out of 30 respondents expressed that they will be very likely to use EasyConveyor for temporary setups like pop-up factories or construction. This indicates strong evidence of the implementation of the EasyConveyor machine will save the cost, time and energy for temporary setups.

Figure 3. Results of questionnaire distributed among UiTM students

Lastly, a significant number, 11 out of 30 respondents, finds EasyConveyor is a practical conveyor machine due to the modular design for easy assembly or disassembly. This demonstrates a clear market demand for reliable technologies that can enhance the process of moving the goods such as export and import products in a practical and easy way.

Figure 4. Results of questionnaire distributed among UiTM students

Based on the survey results, respondents stated that EasyConveyor is an innovation trade product that is new to the market. However, there would be a high demand of the product due the majority of respondents would consider using a battery-powered conveyor system for their worksite or factory. They highlighted that it is very likely to use EasyConveyor for temporary setups like pop-up factories or construction sites to adapt a practical process of moving the goods. Lastly, most of the respondents agreed the most appealing feature of EasyConveyor is for its modular design for easy assembly or disassembly.

6. CONCLUSION AND REFLECTION

Easyconveyor

Belt conveyor material: Rubber

-**Provide a good grip** (The belt used in EasyConveyor is made of high-grade industrial rubber, which provides an excellent grip on the products being conveyed).

- **Durability** -(Rubber belts are often reinforced with materials like steel or fabric to increase their strength and lifespan, allowing the conveyor to handle continuous and rigorous use).

-**Suitable for heavy-duty** (Rubber belts are designed to handle a wide range of materials, from light goods to heavy, bulky items).

Battery made from lithium iron phosphate

- **Safety** (lithium-ion batteries are more thermally and chemically stable, significantly reducing the risk of overheating, combustion, or explosion).

- **Longer life span** (can endure up to 2,000-5,000 charge and discharge cycles, meaning they will last several years under normal usage conditions).

-**Heavy duty** (These batteries are designed to provide consistent power even under high demand).

-Can withstand charge and discharge cycles

Figure 5. EasyConveyor

The EasyConveyor system offers a groundbreaking approach to material handling in industries that demand flexibility, efficiency, and mobility. By incorporating modularity, battery power, and wireless controls, this innovative solution addresses the limitations of traditional conveyor systems. EasyConveyor modular sections allow users to assemble and disassemble the conveyor easily, making it suitable for evolving work environments such as pop-up factories and construction sites. Its battery-powered operation enhances mobility and provides uninterrupted workflow, even in locations with limited power infrastructure. The conveyor's adaptable design supports various configurations, enabling businesses to adjust the conveyor layout as needed, which reduces downtime and costs while improving productivity.

Feedback from the community reveals strong support for Easy Conveyors features, particularly its modular design, mobility, and efficiency. Survey results indicate a high likelihood of adoption among respondents, with many citing the modular, battery-powered system as a practical and cost-effective solution for temporary or flexible setups. In addition, respondents value its ability to meet various operational demands without the complexity and expense of fixed conveyor systems.

In summary, EasyConveyor presents a versatile, user-friendly, and sustainable solution for modern material handling needs. Its commercial potential spans a range of industries where temporary setups, space constraints, and adaptability are essential. By providing a system that is both environmentally conscious and operationally efficient, EasyConveyor has the potential to become a valuable asset for businesses seeking to enhance productivity, lower costs, and stay competitive in dynamic environments.

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